

Effect of Green Water and Mixed Zooplankton on Growth and Survival in Neon Tetra, *Paracheirodon innesi* (Myers, 1936) During Larval and Early Fry Rearing

Authors : S.V. SANAYE, H.S. DHAKER, R.M. TIBILE and V.D. MHATRE

Abstract : Larval rearing and seed production of most of tetra fishes (Family: Characidae) is critical due to their small size larvae and limited numbers of spawning attempts. During the present study the effect of different live foods on growth and survival of neon tetra larvae (length 3.1 ± 0.012 mm, weight 0.048 ± 0.00015 mg) and early fry (length = 6.44 ± 0.025 mm, weight = 0.64 ± 0.003 mg and 13 days old) was determined in two experiments. Experiment I was conducted for rearing the larvae by using mixed green water and Infusoria whereas, in Experiment II, early fry were fed with mixed zooplankton, decapsulated Artemia cyst and Artemia nauplii. The larvae fed on mixed green water showed significant ($p < 0.05$) growth and survival when compared to those fed with infusoria. Similarly, the larvae fed with mixed zooplankton exhibited higher growth in terms of length gain (131.98%), weight gain (6658.78%), SGR (14.04%) and survival (95.23%) compared to the other treatments of decapsulated Artemia cyst and Artemia nauplii. The present study concluded that mixed green water and mixed zooplankton should be used as food for better growth and survival of the larvae and early fry of *P. innesi*, respectively

Keywords : Growth, Mixed Green water, mixed zooplankton, Neon tetra, *Paracheirodon innesi*

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